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Research Article

**FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF FAST DISSOLVING
TABLET OF DAPAGLIFLOZIN**Md Nakib Azam^{*1}, Rahul Mathur², Dr. Jagdish Chandra Rathi³¹Student, NRI Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Bhopal²Associate professor, NRI Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Bhopal³Principal, NRI Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Bhopal**Abstract:**

The present work aimed to enhance the solubility of dapagliflozin through the formation of inclusion complexes with β -cyclodextrin prepared in varying ratios by the physical mixture method. Dapagliflozin was characterized as a yellow, odorless, slightly bitter crystalline solid with a melting point in the range of 67–70 °C. Its physicochemical properties were evaluated, including solubility in different media, partition coefficient ($\log P = 2.6$, indicating moderate lipophilicity), and UV absorption maximum at 221 nm. A calibration curve was established in phosphate buffer (pH 7.4), and compatibility studies confirmed the suitability of selected excipients for fast dissolving tablet formulation. Pre-compression parameters such as bulk density, tapped density, Carr's index, Hausner's ratio, and angle of repose demonstrated good flow properties across all formulations. Post-compression evaluation revealed acceptable ranges for weight variation (202.3–212.2 mg), thickness (2.61–2.78 mm), hardness (2.5–2.8 kg/cm²), friability (0.298–0.395%), disintegration time (23.17–34.62 s), drug content (94.14–99.16%), wetting time (32.17–44.16 s), and water absorption ratio (54.27–58.61%). In vitro dissolution studies showed that cumulative drug release varied among formulations (FDT-1 to FDT-6), with FDT-6 exhibiting the highest release of 97.14% within 30 minutes. These findings confirm that inclusion complexation with β -cyclodextrin significantly improves the solubility and dissolution profile of dapagliflozin, supporting its potential application in fast dissolving tablet formulations for enhanced therapeutic efficacy.

Keywords: Dapagliflozin, Superdisintegrants, Glycaemia, Fast Dissolving Tablet, Solubility

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INTRODUCTION:

Dapagliflozin is a highly potent, selective, competitive inhibitor of sodium glucose co-transporter-2 (SGLT2), improves glycaemic control in patients with Type 2 diabetes (T2DM) by reducing renal glucose re-absorption¹. Dapagliflozin belongs to BCS class III drug, and have a bad metallic taste². Since, the solubility of dapagliflozin is low in aqueous phase hence inclusion complex will be formed to enhance the solubility³. The formulation of dapagliflozin fast dissolving tablet will enhance the absorption and bioavailability will get faster and hence the drug will show rapid onset of action.

Fast dissolving tablets are novel drug delivery system that dissolves, disintegrate or disperse the API in saliva within few seconds with or without intake of water⁴. The faster the dissolution of drug into the solution, quicker is the absorption and onset of clinical effect⁵. The bioavailability of some drugs may increase due to absorption of drugs in oral cavity or also due to pregastric absorption of drug from saliva that pass down into the stomach⁶. Natural and synthetic superdisintegrants like mucilage cross linked carboxymethyl cellulose (crosscarmellose) and sodium starch glycolate (Primogel), poly vinyl pyrrolidone, etc. provide immediate disintegration of tablets and facilitate the design of delivery system with desirable characteristics⁷. These types of formulations are widely recommended for the drugs used in emergency. e.g., Cardiac agents, asthma, Brain stroke, Anti-hyper-lipidemic etc⁸. The fast dissolving tablets of dapagliflozin prepare employing different concentrations of a superdisintegrants by Direct Compression technique⁹. The formulation will enhance the absorption as well as the bioavailability of the drug leading to rapid onset of action¹⁰. The main aim of current research is to formulate and evaluate fast dissolving tablet of dapagliflozin using superdisintegrant to produce dosage form having rapid onset of action.

MATERIALS AND METHOD:

Formulation of fast dissolving tablet:

Dapagliflozin was obtained from Novartis Pharmaceuticals Hyderabad as gift and Beta-cyclodextrin was purchased from Chem Center. The solvents and reagents used were belongs to lab reagent grade.

Formulation of Fast Dissolving Tablet: The manual experiments were performed for the formulation of fast dissolving tablet of Dapagliflozin and the experimental trials were performed at six formulations, in which the concentrations (1:2) of drug and β -cyclodextrin, different concentrations of superdisintegrants (Sodium starch glycolate) which were varied from lower to higher concentrations. Microcrystalline cellulose as fillers, Mannitol as binder and sweetener, Saccharin sodium as sweetener, were also used in formulation. Fast dissolving tablet of Dapagliflozin was prepared using Kneading method.

Preparation of β -cyclodextrin inclusion complex: β -cyclodextrin was mixed with a minimum amount of solvent (water) to form a thick paste. Slowly, the drug was incorporated into the slurry while kneading continuously in a mortar. Mixture was continuously kneaded for 30–60 minutes to ensure uniform mixing that facilitated complex formation. The kneaded mass was dried in oven at 40–50 °C until moisture is removed. The dried mass grinds and passed through a sieve to obtain a fine powder. Final inclusion complex kept in desiccator to avoid moisture uptake.

Preparation of fast dissolving tablet by direct compression: Fast dissolving tablets of Dapagliflozin were prepared by direct compression method. All the ingredients were weighed accurately. All the ingredients were mixed step by step with drug: β -cyclodextrin inclusion complex and triturated continuously for 15 minute. Subsequently talc and magnesium stearate mixed at last & again mixed. Then passed through sieve no. #60. Powder was compressed using multi-station tablet punching machine with 8mm flat punch, B-tooling and corresponding dies.

Table No. 1: Composition of Fast Dissolving Tablet

Ingredients	FDT-1	FDT-2	FDT-3	FDT-4	FDT-5	FDT-6
Dapagliflozin (mg)	10	10	10	10	10	10
β - cyclodextrin (mg)	20	20	20	20	20	20
Sodium starch glycolate (mg)	3	4	5	6	7	8
Microcrystalline cellulose (mg)	120	120	120	120	120	120
Mannitol (mg)	30	30	30	30	30	30
Saccharin sodium (mg)	10	10	10	10	10	10
Magnesium Stearate (mg)	4	4	4	4	4	4
Talc (mg)	6	6	6	6	6	6
Total (mg)	203	204	205	206	207	208

Evaluation of Inclusion Complex by Solubility Determination: An excess amount of prepared Dapagliflozin: β -cyclodextrin inclusion complex at concentration (1:2) were separately dissolved in 5 ml phosphate buffer pH 7.4 in vials and sealed properly and stirred continuously at 37 ± 2 °C. The process was repeated until saturation solubility of inclusion complex. The solution was kept for 24 hours at room temperature. The solution was filtered and adequately diluted with phosphate buffer pH 7.4. Solution was analyzed using UV-visible spectrophotometer at 221 nm.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Preformulation study:

The drug sample was examined for its color, odor, taste etc. the dapagliflozin was yellow, odorless, slight bitter crystalline solid. The melting point of dapagliflozin was observed in the range of 67 to 70 °C starts to melt.

Solubility of Dapagliflozin: The solubility of Dapagliflozin in various mediums was studied and the results of study were shown in below table:

Table No. 2: Solubility data of Dapagliflozin in different mediums

S. No.	Solvent	Solubility (mg/ml) Mean \pm SD
1	Methanol	44.27 \pm 0.52
2	Phosphate buffer pH 7.4	0.894 \pm 0.02
3	pH 1.2 HCl	0.508 \pm 0.14
4	Distilled water	0.107 \pm 0.12

Solubility of inclusion complex: The solubility of inclusion complex in phosphate buffer pH 7.4 was studied and the results of study were shown in below table:

Table No. 3: Solubility data of inclusion complex

S. No.	Drug/ β -CD Complex	Solubility (mg/ml) Mean \pm SD
1	Pure drug	0.894 \pm 0.02
2	Drug: β -CD (1:1)	9.416 \pm 0.16
3	Drug: β -CD (1:2)	12.751 \pm 0.21

The partition coefficient (Log P) of dapagliflozin was observed as 2.6 indicating moderate lipophilicity. The drug (Dapagliflozin) was found to be compatible with various excipients which were selected for formulation of fast dissolving tablet. Determination of wavelength using UV spectroscopy: The maximum wavelength of Dapagliflozin was found to be 221 nm. A calibration curve of dapagliflozin in phosphate buffer pH 7.4 was prepared.

Figure 1: Calibration graph of Dapagliflozin in phosphate buffer pH 7.4 at 221 nm

Evaluation of Precompression Parameters of Powder: The bulk density, tapped density, Carr's index, Hausner's ratio and angle of repose of selected formulations were performed. The results showed that the all formulations possessed a good flow property.

Table No. 4: Evaluation of precompression parameters of powder

Formulation Code	Bulk density (gm/ml) (Mean \pm SD)	Tapped density (gm/ml) (Mean \pm SD)	Carr's index (%) (Mean \pm SD)	Hausner's ratio (Mean \pm SD)	Angle of repose (o) (Mean \pm SD)
FDT-1	0.355 \pm 0.002	0.414 \pm 0.001	14.389 \pm 0.23	1.16 \pm 0.03	26.62 \pm 0.17
FDT-2	0.302 \pm 0.008	0.353 \pm 0.002	14.513 \pm 0.92	1.16 \pm 0.01	29.12 \pm 0.28
FDT-3	0.315 \pm 0.002	0.376 \pm 0.001	16.370 \pm 0.35	1.19 \pm 0.04	28.92 \pm 0.73
FDT-4	0.327 \pm 0.007	0.383 \pm 0.005	14.692 \pm 1.01	1.16 \pm 0.02	27.25 \pm 0.34
FDT-5	0.285 \pm 0.008	0.337 \pm 0.007	15.590 \pm 1.17	1.18 \pm 0.02	29.24 \pm 0.16
FDT-6	0.356 \pm 0.003	0.405 \pm 0.004	12.243 \pm 1.12	1.13 \pm 0.02	25.18 \pm 0.20

Evaluation of Post-Compression Parameters of Fast Dissolving Tablet: The fast dissolving tablet of Dapagliflozin were evaluated like weight variation, hardness, thickness, friability, disintegration time, drug content, wetting time and water absorption ratio. The results of the studies were shown in below table:

Table No. 5: Weight variation, Hardness, Thickness, and Friability of Formulation

Formulation Code	Weight variation (mg) (Mean \pm SD)	Thickness (mm) (Mean \pm SD)	Hardness (Kg/cm ²) (Mean \pm SD)	Friability (%) (Mean \pm SD)
FDT-1	202.3 \pm 1.50	2.69 \pm 0.04	2.7 \pm 0.11	0.335 \pm 0.01
FDT-2	206.8 \pm 1.15	2.63 \pm 0.07	2.6 \pm 0.12	0.298 \pm 0.03
FDT-3	205.2 \pm 1.08	2.61 \pm 0.01	2.5 \pm 0.07	0.357 \pm 0.02
FDT-4	206.4 \pm 1.20	2.70 \pm 0.03	2.6 \pm 0.14	0.372 \pm 0.04
FDT-5	208.3 \pm 2.11	2.74 \pm 0.05	2.6 \pm 0.12	0.395 \pm 0.07
FDT-6	212.2 \pm 1.15	2.78 \pm 0.05	2.8 \pm 0.09	0.358 \pm 0.01

Table No. 6: Disintegration Time, Drug Content, Wetting time & water absorption Ratio of Formulation

Formulation Code	Disintegration Time (sec) Mean \pm SD	Drug Content (%) Mean \pm SD	Wetting time (sec) Mean \pm SD	Water absorption Ratio (%) Mean \pm SD
FDT-1	24.47 \pm 0.235	94.14 \pm 0.65	32.17 \pm 0.14	58.19 \pm 0.25
FDT-2	33.14 \pm 0.365	96.38 \pm 0.67	36.23 \pm 0.66	58.61 \pm 0.57
FDT-3	31.21 \pm 0.429	99.16 \pm 0.90	38.15 \pm 0.91	54.27 \pm 0.93
FDT-4	34.37 \pm 0.179	96.54 \pm 0.44	44.16 \pm 0.59	58.45 \pm 0.83
FDT-5	34.62 \pm 0.268	96.11 \pm 0.05	35.23 \pm 0.24	57.61 \pm 0.59
FDT-6	23.17 \pm 0.133	98.62 \pm 0.84	34.62 \pm 0.48	54.29 \pm 0.73

In-vitro Drug Release Study of Fast Dissolving Tablet:

The percentage cumulative drug release from formulations FDT-1 to FDT-6 was determined. The formulation FDT-6 showed the highest release (%) within 30 minutes.

Figure 2: Cumulative % drug release of FDT-1 to FDT-6 formulation

CONCLUSION:

The present research work envisaged the applicability of superdisintegrants (sodium starch glycolate) in the design and development of fast dissolving formulation of Dapagliflozin by manual experiments. In the present work solubility of drug was enhanced by using inclusion complex. The inclusion complex of drug: β -cyclodextrin was prepared in different ratios by physical mixture method.

The direct compression method was used to formulate and evaluate fast dissolving tablet of dapagliflozin. The formulation prepared were evaluated for precompression studies such as bulk density, tapped density, Carr's index, Hausner's ratio and angle of repose which were found to be within limits. The increased concentration of the superdisintegrants enhanced the porosity of the tablet, due to which it reduced the disintegration time and wetting time and maximum drug release in 30 minutes. Compressed tablets were evaluated for post-compression studies like weight variation, hardness, thickness, friability, disintegration, drug content which were found to be good. It was concluded that the addition of drug: β -cyclodextrin inclusion complex leads to improved solubility of drug at optimum concentration (1:2). From all the results it is concluded that formulation FDT-6 containing crospovidone was found to be the best formulation in terms of flow property, disintegration time, wetting time, drug content and maximum percentage drug release. It was observed that formulation FDT-6 shown rapid disintegration time, wetting time and highest percentage cumulative drug release within 30 minutes.

Thus the present study demonstrated the potential of the formulated fast dissolving tablet for rapid absorption, improved bioavailability, effective therapy and improved patient compliance.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

There are no conflicts of interests.

REFERENCES:

1. Ayush Kartikey, Anshita Gupta, Dr. Vivek Gupta. Formulation and evaluation of bilayer tablet of dapagliflozin and vildagliptin. *Jptcp*, 2023, 30(1):714-723.
2. Kajal More, Amreen Khan, Umesh Atreria, Neeraj Sharma, Dharmendra Solanki. Formulation and Evaluation of Fast Dissolving Tablet of Dapagliflozin. *Ijsdr*, 2024;9(4): 1466-1472.
3. Gadhwala Sofiza Z, Maulik R. Mehta. Formulation and Characterization of Sublingual Film of Dapagliflozin Propanediol Monohydrate. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research and Applications*.

2023;8(6): 2781-88.

4. Patil, M R. Gujarathi, N A. Rane, B R. (2014) "Formulation And Evaluation of Mouth Dissolving Tablet: Review Article", *Pharma Science Monitor*, 5(2),9
5. Duppala, L. Girinath, S K. Kumar, D M. (2016) "Fast Dissolving Dosage Forms: An Overview" *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 5(10),1185-1186.
6. Singh, S. (2014) "Review on Fast Dissolving Tablets", *International Journal of Pharmamedix India*, 2(3),819-820.
7. Khanna, K. Xavier, G. Joshi, S K. Patel, A. Khanna, S. Goel, B V. (2016) "Fast Dissolving Tablets- A Novel Approach" *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research Allied Sciences*, 5(2),311-312.
8. Masih, A. Kumar, A. Singh, S. Tiwari, A K (2017) "Fast Dissolving Tablets: A Review" *International Journal of Current Pharmaceutical Research*, 9(2),8.
9. Saxena, S. Yadav, N (2017) "Fast Dissolving Tablets: A Big Turn in Pharmaceutical Industry" *Research and Reviews Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 6(1),26.
10. Carrier, R L. Miller, L A. Ahmed, I. (2007) "The utility of cyclodextrins for enhancing oral bioavailability", *J Control Release*, 123,78-99.